

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIBRE ASSEMBLIES AND TEXTILE UNIT CELLS

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the modelling of mechanical properties of dry textile unit cells, aimed primarily at predicting material behaviour for fabric draping analyses. This is split into two main parts, modelling of the individual fibres within a tow and modelling of textile unit cells. Modelling of the individual fibres yields a material model which is used to describe the deformation behaviour of an equivalent continuum solid under various loading conditions. Continuum solid elements representing the tows are then used to model textile unit cells using finite element analysis software, in order to predict reinforcement deformation behaviour during processing.

KEYWORDS: Mechanical Properties, Textile, Dry Fabric, Tow, Fibre Compaction, X-ray Microtomography, Multi-scale Modelling

INTRODUCTION

In order to model the geometry of textiles in an efficient way for mechanical property predictions, the textile modelling software TexGen was developed [1]. TexGen is a software application written in C++ to model all textiles in 3D using the same unified format. The format involves describing the yarn/tow paths with the use of vectors for a repeatable unit cell. Only a small number of vectors are needed to model the geometry of most textiles, typically one vector per tow cross-over. The vector paths are then smoothed automatically using piecewise cubic Bézier curves. In order to give the tows a volume an arbitrary cross-sectional shape is assigned to the paths. Furthermore, the cross section can be meshed using 2D triangular elements which, once swept along the length of the tow path, generate 3D wedge/prism elements. The model is then exported to finite element analysis software for dry fabric mechanical property analysis which is important for draping of textile composite preforms.

Modelling of the individual fibres within a tow for a unit cell model such as one created by TexGen is very computationally expensive (so much so that it is virtually impossible for tows with high fibre count). Therefore it is convenient to model tows as solids with given non-linear anisotropic mechanical properties. This is expected to yield a reasonable first approximation for the static behaviour of the textile; however the appropriate tow mechanical properties must be obtained. A number of analytical tow models exist to obtain some or all of these mechanical properties [2-8], although in each of these models certain fitting parameters must be determined experimentally. Here an alternative approach is taken to attempt to determine these mechanical properties through computer simulation taking into account the complexities of the fibre interactions in a more realistic manner.

UNIT CELL MODELLING

Modelling the mechanical properties of dry fabrics using finite element analysis [9] and other techniques [10] has been carried out for various fabrics in the past. In this paper, a very generic method to perform finite element analysis of dry fabrics applicable to almost all types of fabrics is described.

Tow Paths

The geometry of many undeformed textiles can be defined as a unit cell which is repeated in two orthogonal directions. It is therefore possible to define an infinitely large textile simply by specifying the geometry within the unit cell and the repeat distances. Within TexGen the geometry of the tows within the unit cell is defined by the paths of their centrelines. Each path is defined by a list of points given in 3D space; these points are then connected together by vectors. This is a convenient way to model the geometry of continuous tows.

Vector Smoothing

In order to provide a smooth continuous path for the tows piecewise cubic Bézier curves are used. This is a generic way to obtain a smooth curve which passes through all of the vector ends no matter where they are positioned. Four control points are defined for each vector with the first and last control points corresponding to the origin and end of the vector respectively. The two middle control points are positioned in such a way to conserve first order continuity with adjacent Bézier curves. There is not a single unique position configuration for the middle control points that will provide first order continuity. Some control is available to adjust the shape of the curve.

Tow Shape

The shape of the tow may be defined independently from its path which allows for small changes in the tow shape without having to redefine the paths. The shape of the tows may be created from a list of pre-defined shapes given a set of parameters (e.g. ellipse with given width and height). Alternatively, completely arbitrary shapes may be created, defined by a list of points connected together by straight lines which follow the perimeter of the tow. Once the tow shape has been defined it can be assigned to the vector paths to create a full 3D model. Any number of tow shapes may be defined and assigned to different tows and/or different sections along the length of the tow. The shape of the tow will depend on the type of fabric and manufacturing process. For plain woven fabrics the cross section takes a lenticular shape, while non-crimp fabrics can be characterised as power-ellipses (slightly modified ellipses that have more rectangular edges). Once the cross sections are assigned to the paths there may be regions of space occupied by two different tows (i.e. interference between the tows). There is an algorithm in place to attempt to remove these interferences before the mesh generation process [11].

Mesh Generation

TexGen is able to create a 3D mesh for the tows directly without using commercial 3rd party software. The procedure consists of first meshing the cross sections with triangular elements. The cross sections are planar so this is essentially a 2D meshing problem. The triangular meshing is performed by open source code, Triangle [12]. Maximum element area and minimum angle can be varied to obtain different degrees of mesh refinement. The mesh is then copied, translated and rotated into 3D space to fit to each of the nodes along the length of

the tow. The nodes of the triangular elements on adjacent cross sections are joined together to form prism/wedge elements (Fig. 1). In order to obtain good quality elements the distance between the cross sections must be as close as possible to the triangle edge lengths. Since the distance cannot be varied on a triangle to triangle basis, the average edge length of all of the triangles is calculated and used to optimise the distance between cross sections. A similar procedure could be adopted to create hexahedral elements by meshing the cross sections using quadrilateral elements. Perhaps the optimum would be to create a hybrid hexahedral/wedge mesh from quadrilateral/triangle cross-sectional meshes. However, this would require a more complex 2D meshing algorithm.

Fig. 1: Wedge/Prism mesh for a plain weave generated by TexGen.

An immediately noticeable feature of these meshes generated by TexGen is that the boundaries of the unit cell are not necessarily planar. In conventional solid modelling, one would trim the tow volumes to fit within a box with orthogonal faces. This can lead to difficult volumes to mesh, prohibiting the use of a swept cross section approach in some cases, hence restricting the meshing technique to more conforming techniques such as tetrahedral meshing. These techniques give poorer quality meshes, so should be avoided. Planar boundaries are not a requirement when using periodic boundary conditions. Provided that the nodes from one face of the boundary match up with those on the opposite face, periodic boundary conditions may be applied. This is done by linking the relevant degrees of freedom of corresponding nodes on opposite boundary faces.

Initial Stresses

TexGen describes the result of a weaving/braiding or other textile manufacturing process. These processes will induce stresses and strains within the tows due to the bending of the tows. The initial stress-free state of the tows is assumed to be when they are straight. Very small stresses may still exist within the tow due to bending of individual fibres held in by frictional forces however these can be taken into account by the tow material model. It is reasonable to assume that when the tow is modelled as a continuum that it is in a stress-free state when the tows are straight. The strains can be incorporated by simple geometrical considerations, these strains will in turn result in stresses determined by the material model.

By creating the mesh directly within TexGen it is possible to output a finite element analysis input file for ABAQUSTM which contains these initial element strains. The geometry created with TexGen may contain small gaps between crossing tows, these gaps will disappear if the

finite element analysis is left to run with no external applied loads. The internal stresses will cause the tows to attempt to straighten, this will be prevented when the tows come into contact (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Gaps removed through initial element strains.

Material Model

A tow's mechanical properties can be characterised as a transversely isotropic material such that the mechanical properties across the tow cross section are isotropic while the mechanical properties in the direction of the tow are different [13]. This leads to seven material properties: E_L , E_T , ν_{TT} , ν_{TL} , ν_{LT} , G_{LT} , G_{TT} , two of which can be determined from the others (Eqn. (1) and (2)).

$$\frac{\nu_{TL}}{E_T} = \frac{\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{TT} = \frac{E_T}{2(1 + \nu_{TT})} \quad (2)$$

For the purposes of finite element analysis, the most convenient form to characterise the mechanical properties is that of the stiffness matrix (Eqn. (3) and (4)).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{zx} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1 - \nu_{TT}^2}{E_T^2 \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{TL} + \nu_{TT} \nu_{TL}}{E_T^2 \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{TL} + \nu_{TT} \nu_{TL}}{E_T^2 \Delta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{LT} + \nu_{TT} \nu_{LT}}{E_T E_L \Delta} & \frac{1 - \nu_{TL} \nu_{LT}}{E_T E_L \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{TT} + \nu_{TL} \nu_{LT}}{E_T E_L \Delta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{LT} + \nu_{TT} \nu_{LT}}{E_T E_L \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{TT} + \nu_{TL} \nu_{LT}}{E_T E_L \Delta} & \frac{1 - \nu_{TL} \nu_{LT}}{E_T E_L \Delta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{LT} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{TT} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{LT} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{zz} \\ \epsilon_{xy} \\ \epsilon_{yz} \\ \epsilon_{zx} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta = \frac{(1 + \nu_T)(1 - \nu_T - 2\nu_{TL}\nu_{LT})}{E_T^2 E_L} \quad (4)$$

Experimental Comparison

Experimental and FE shear tests were performed on a plain weave fabric (Vetrotex RT600). The longitudinal modulus of the tow was determined by multiplying the fibre volume fraction of the tow by the modulus of the fibres yielding a value of 60000 N/mm^2 . The transverse modulus was chosen to be very small in comparison to the longitudinal modulus (1000 N/mm^2). Transverse Poisson's ratio was set at 0.3 while the other two Poisson's ratio were set at 0. Transverse shear modulus was determined based on transverse modulus and Poisson's ratio as shown in Eqn. (2) (385 N/mm^2). The other two shear moduli were set to the same value for convenience as accurate data for these properties were not available. The coefficient of friction was assumed to be 0.3 as no experimental data for this value was obtained. The geometrical model was based on the real fabric where lenticular cross-sectional tow shapes were assumed. The model consisted of 3528 prism elements.

Presently the values of shear force for the finite element tests do not correlate well with the experimental results for reasons discussed later. However the trends do correlate well: Fig. 3 shows a graph of shear force vs. shear angle where the finite element analysis where scaled down by a factor of 250. The fluctuations in the finite element analysis data are due to the explicit method used where the kinetic energy in the system causes artificial forces. Damping can be used to control the fluctuations, however too much damping can lead to large drag forces giving an overestimate of the shear force. The drag forces can be compensated for to some extent by shifting the curve along the Y axis.

Fig. 3: Graph of shear force vs. shear angle for RT600 plain weave fabric.

The reason for the large scale disagreement between the finite element analysis and the experimental results may be due to the rather arbitrary material model used. In reality a large number of the material properties that have been assumed to be constant are non-linear. For example, the compressive transverse modulus of a tow is highly non-linear. The transverse modulus will affect the contact force between the tows hence affecting the frictional forces which play an important part in the shear properties of a fabric. Transverse Poisson's ratio and shear moduli are also likely to be highly non-linear but are very difficult to measure experimentally. The axial tension is almost linear, with only very slight non-linearity at low strains when the fibres tend to straighten [4]. In order to improve the accuracy of the results

there is a requirement for an improved material model, the development of which is described in the following section.

MODELLING OF TOW MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

A series of papers has been written on analytical models for the compaction of fibre assemblies, each one building on its predecessors [3, 5, 6, 8]. The first dates back to 1946 and was written by van Wyk [2]. He proposed an analytical model for the compression of randomly oriented wool fibres which in contrast to continuous fibre tows, have no preferential fibre direction. More specifically, he determined the pressure applied to an assembly of fibres as a function of the bounding volume occupied by the fibres. van Wyk simplified the problem by assuming that the only force resisting the compression of fibre assemblies is the bending of fibres caused by fibre to fibre point contacts. The average distance between contact points along the length of a fibre is calculated by taking the total length of fibre within the bounding volume and dividing by twice the total number of contacts within that volume. With the average distance between contacts known and assuming that the fibres bend following the Euler-Bernoulli beam equation for a point load applied at the centre of a beam with built-in ends, an equation for the pressure necessary to compress the fibre assembly is obtained. Due to the large number of assumptions made two values in the equation must be determined experimentally, and used to fit the curve to the experimental data.

Gutowski and Cai developed a theory for the deformation behaviour of aligned fibres suitable for production of composite materials [7]. The shape of each individual fibre is assumed to follow a sine wave with arc length and height as parameters to be determined. In order to obtain a stress-strain relationship for transverse compression of the fibre assembly a single fibre is enclosed within a bounding box. The compressive modulus of the fibre assembly is assumed to be the same as the compressive modulus of the bounding box containing this single fibre.

A method to determine the tow mechanical properties via computer simulation is proposed here. The transverse compaction behaviour of the tows will be studied initially. The axial tension can be assumed to have a Young's modulus equal to that of the modulus of the fibres multiplied by the volume fraction of the tow. It is also important to investigate shear behaviour, however experimental data are difficult to obtain, making validation challenging.

In order to perform the simulation, an in-house package is under development. The simulation consists of modelling the fibres as circular cross-sectional beams with the ability to bend following the well known Euler-Bernoulli beam bending equations with the law of superposition. The deflections are caused by the interactions with other fibres including frictional forces. This bending effect is assumed to be the only factor contributing to the deformation of the tow. The change in length of the fibres due to bending is assumed to be negligible, fibres are assumed to have a circular cross section and fibres are assumed to be initially straight but slightly misaligned.

Initial Fibre Distribution

The initial distribution of fibres within a tow has been measured experimentally by scanning a tow using x-ray microtomography (MicroCT). A program has been developed to analyse the data obtained from the MicroCT scan. Similar work has been performed for assemblies of random short fibres [14]. The major difficulty is that the resolution of the scanner is of $6\mu\text{m}$, while the diameter of the fibres is approximately $15\mu\text{m}$. This limitation in resolution makes it difficult to identify individual fibres. Nevertheless the program is able to identify the centre

lines of the fibres with reasonable accuracy; a straight line is then fitted to the fibres to obtain a direction vector for each fibre. The fibres do tend to be straight over the length of scan measured (approximately 2mm). Fig. 4 shows the data reconstructed using a generic algorithm (marching cubes) with the determined centre-lines overlaid as well as the distribution of fibre angles deviating from the average fibre direction. The tow scanned was from a Twintex tow which contains a mix of glass and polypropylene fibres, only the glass fibres are visible with x-rays.

Fig. 4: Tow fibre geometry data from MicroCT for Twintex tow.

Fibre Contacts

For the purpose of simplifying the contact algorithm, the 3D problem is divided into a large number of 2D problems. Cross sections along the length of the tow axis are taken at regular intervals (Fig. 5), and it is along these cross sections that the contacts are determined. This is reasonable as the fibres are all more or less aligned along the same axis, hence the forces due to contact will always be approximately in the plane perpendicular to this axis for all loading cases except for shearing along the length of the tow.

Fig. 5: Fibres within the domain (left), fibres split into cross sections (right).

For each tow cross section inter-fibre contacts are determined by finding intersections between fibres. An iterative method is used to calculate the final equilibrium state of the tow where the contacting fibres are just touching without any penetration. At each iteration the contact force between fibres is increased by a factor proportional to penetration allowing the solution to converge. Similarly if fibres which were previously in contact are pushed apart, the contact force between them is decreased by a factor proportional to the clearance. Once all the forces have been accumulated for the current iteration, the new deflected shape of the fibres can be calculated for the next iteration. The iterations are repeated until a steady state of equilibrium is reached, that is to say that all the fibres are just contacting each other and the forces no longer change after subsequent iterations. A tolerance is used here to ensure the simulation runs within a reasonable time-scale.

Fibre Bending

The Euler-Bernoulli beam bending equations are used to calculate the deflections, slope, moment and shear force at any point along the length of the fibre. A small section of tow contained within a domain is analysed at once, hence appropriate boundary conditions are needed. For fibres within the domain, the ends are assumed to be fixed with pin-joints. These boundary conditions are still under investigation and more appropriate conditions may be applied in the future. The boundary conditions for the cross sections are periodic.

For each cross section of the tow, there may be more than one force acting on the beam, in which case the forces are resolved to determine a resultant force. In addition it is likely that forces will be acting on a fibre at several different cross sections along the tow. Instead of attempting to solve the deflection of the fibre due to all of these forces in one step, a method of superposition is used: First of all the deflection due to each individual force acting on a fibre is calculated one at a time. Then the final deflection is calculated by superimposing all of these deflections together (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Superposition of beam deflections due to two separate forces.

Transverse Tow Compression

In order to simulate the transverse compression of a tow, it is necessary to perform the task over a number of small steps. At each step, the tow will be compressed by a small amount and a new state of equilibrium must be reached (which is done over a finite number of iterations) before moving on to the next step. The compression is simulated by scaling the coordinates of

the ends of the fibres (i.e. at the pin jointed ends) along an axis perpendicular to the fibre direction while keeping the radii of the fibres constant. The total strain energy stored within the tow is calculated at each step. The work done by external forces is force multiplied by distance. The strain energy within the tow must be equal to the work done on it; hence the force and pressure may be determined. The compression modulus at each stage may also be calculated which is expected to change as a function of compression.

The results from the computational model were compared against the Gutowski model [7]. The Gutowski model has been shown to fit experimental data very well when the parameters are adjusted to fit. The β parameter used to fit to the computation model is very large compared to that used to fit experimental data, however this parameter only affects the scale of the pressure, not the shape of the curve. The other parameters are consistent with those used for fitting to experimental data. Therefore it can be concluded that the trend is correct, although predicted pressures are significantly lower than experimental data obtained by McBride [4]. The reason that the computational model pressure curve is not smooth is that it is taken as the derivative of the strain energy curve. Hence any abnormalities in the strain energy curve are greatly amplified in the pressure curve. It should be noted that the number of fibres analysed in the computational model was around 40 whereas a tow contains thousands of fibres, hence individual fibres have a large impact on the result resulting in larger fluctuations than in the real case. At present the computational model is not able to represent large levels of compaction, so the range of the graph is limited; the system becomes unstable when the number of fibre contacts increases above a certain point. In the case of the graph below the fibres were assumed to deviate from the tow axis by a normally distributed random value, where the standard deviation was determined from the MicroCT scans. The modulus of the fibres were taken to be 70 GPa.

Fig. 7: Plot of Gutowski model fitted to computational model.
 $(V_a = 0.85, V_0 = 0.4, \beta = 20000, E_f = 70 \text{ GPa})$.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the modelling of the geometry of textile unit cells is discussed. A mesh generation technique which is suitable for use with periodic boundary conditions is presented. The material model needed to determine the dry fabric mechanical properties using finite

element analysis techniques is discussed. A comparison of FE and experimental results shows similar trends however the scale is very different, this is thought to be largely due to the simplified tow material properties used.

In order to obtain more realistic material properties for the tow, a computational model analysing the mechanical behaviour of tows is discussed. The tow geometric data is obtained using x-ray microtomography. Similar trends in transverse compaction behaviour are shown from the computational model when compared with experimental data.

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